

SECTION OF BIOLOGICAL AND MEDICAL SCIENCES

ПАТОГЕННЫЕ ГРИБЫ В РАСТЕНИЯХ ПОЛУОСТРОВА АПСШЕРОН

Абдуллаева Ш.А.

Д.б.н. преподаватель

Азербайджанский Государственный Педагогический Университет

PATHOGENIC FUNGI IN THE PLANTS OF THE APSHERON PENINSULA

Abdullaeva Sh.

Doctor of Biological Sciences teacher

Azerbaijan State Pedagogical University

Аннотация

Грибковое заболевание является одним из широко распространенных заболеваний. Мы часто находим его почти на каждом возделываемом поле, в цветах и в листьях деревьев. Мир грибов характеризуется разнообразием образа жизни. Они паразитируют в органах растения и снижают его продуктивность и качественные показатели. Питается готовой органикой. Основные виды грибов имеют микроскопические размеры. У них есть вегетативный орган, состоящий из клещей, и через него они питаются, размножаются и развиваются. В ходе исследовательской работы у многих растений в садах Апшерона было обнаружено большое количество грибковых заболеваний.

Болезнетворные грибы делятся на экзогенные (внешние) и эндогенные (внутренние) виды в зависимости от их распространения в органах растений. В первом случае основные органы размножения и развития распространяются на верхние слои листа. Примерами таких грибов являются возбудители мучнистой росы. Они образуют покрытия и плесень на растениях.

Abstract

Fungal disease is one of the most widespread diseases. We often find it in almost every cultivated field, in flowers and in the leaves of trees. The world of mushrooms is characterized by a variety of lifestyles. They parasitize in plant organs and reduce its productivity and quality indicators. It feeds on prepared organic matter. The main types of fungi are microscopic in size. They have a vegetative organ, consisting of ticks, and through it they feed, multiply and develop. In the course of research work, a large number of fungal diseases were found in many plants in the gardens of Absheron.

Pathogenic fungi are divided into exogenous (external) and endogenous (internal) species, depending on their distribution in plant organs. In the first case, the main organs of reproduction and development extend to the upper layers of the leaf.

Ключевые слова: Абшеронский полуостров, грибковые заболевания, фитопатогенные грибы.

Keywords: Absheron peninsula, fungal diseases, phytopathogenic fungi.

Vegetables and fruits play an important role in human nutrition. Thus, they are the main supplier of vitamins (especially vitamin C and carotene), carbohydrates, organic acids and various minerals, including trace elements. However, the presence of a large amount of water in vegetables and fruits makes their storage impractical. Damaged and diseased fruits and vegetables are especially prone to spoilage, since microorganisms penetrate them relatively easily. The causative agents of fruits and vegetables include *Fusarium*, *Penicillium*, *Aspergillus* from the genera of microscopic fungi that cause various types of spoilage (dry rot, bitter rot). In the process of infection with these pathogens, their metabolites, mycotoxins, accumulate in fruits and vegetables. Studies show that apple bitter rot can be caused by patulin, which has carcinogenic properties. Therefore, the amount of patulin in food products should be at a level acceptable by sanitary standards. In accordance with sanitary require-

ments, rotten fruits and vegetables infected with diseases and pests, rodents, insects and larvae, as well as having a pungent odor and pesticides, are not allowed for sale. Proper harvesting of fruits and vegetables, providing good storage conditions, preventing the development of diseases and their occurrence is considered an effective measure. During storage, it is necessary to create such conditions that vegetables and potatoes are not allowed to grow and germinate. For this purpose, it is proposed to treat potatoes with methyl ester with α -naphthylacetic acid at the rate of 50-100 mg per 1 kg of tuber, which prevents the tubers from turning blue and rotting after a year and contributes to the preservation of ascorbic acid. The optimum temperature for storing fruits and vegetables is 1-2°C, relative humidity 80-85%. Vegetables and fruits can be epidemiologically dangerous. So, a vegetable can be considered a source of gastrointestinal infections and helminthiasis. According to sanitary standards, it is strictly forbidden to water watermelon plants with sewage, to

use them raw (carrots, cucumbers, tomatoes, watermelons, nuts, strawberries, parsley, radishes). Harvesting of fruit and berry plants irrigated with dirty water is stopped after two months, and vegetable plants - after 20 days. The use of vegetables grown on such a field (potatoes, eggplants, eggplants) is allowed after hot processing. The use of chemicals, as well as mineral and other fertilizers in protecting plants from diseases and pests, leads to the intensification of the production of modern agricultural products. Plant protection products are strictly regulated and controlled by the sanitary-veterinary and sanitary-epidemiological services. At the same time, contamination with pesticides occurs when hygienic standards are not observed in the preparation of feed and a number of products of plant and animal origin. Permissible norms for pesticides in feed for farm animals have also been developed. [1, p.743].

During the study, the fungal diseases listed below were detected. Root rot and stem rot are representatives of the group of saprotrophic fungi of soil origin. At high humidity of the substrate, seedlings, like productive plants, develop a coating similar to white mold in a 2-14 cm area near the soil. First of all, in the area of the body in contact with the soil, small whitish-gray and white rounded, elliptical eggs are observed. Later,

white molds form in this area. In areas covered with white mold, thinning and subsequent decay are observed. The disease causes wilting and rotting of the roots and roots of seedlings, the plant falls off. Tomato fruits become infected with the disease and are observed with decay. In polyethylene-lined greenhouses, the disease causes large yield losses in conditions of high temperature and humidity limits [2,p.225].

Rhizopus sp. - rot. The disease occurs in ripening fruits. Infected parts grow as a result of uniform division and the fruits are deformed, commercial qualities are reduced. The swollen parts are covered with white bloom (mycelium and fruiting body of the pathogen). Starting from the lower part, a row of sporangia, accompanied by black and brown dots, cover the entire rotten part within a few days. Within 5-7 days, the tomato fruit softens and rots. A specific smell of fermentation comes from the rotten part. During the years of mass distribution, the product reaches 32-40% of the product. Partial contamination makes the product unsuitable for transportation and storage. To maintain a healthy crop in the tomato distribution area, grading should be carried out at harvest time and damage to the fruit should be avoided. The use of varieties with hard shells is effective in controlling the disease (picture 1).

Picture 1

In fruit, line rot spreads during fruit ripening. The fruits begin to rot from the stem part. On the fruits from the stem part, furrows directed downwards are formed, which deepen as the fruit ripens. In the recesses, a whitish-gray coating of the fungus is observed. When planting tomatoes in open and closed ground without rotation, the incidence of the disease increases if agrotechnical measures are not followed [4,p.500].

The disease called "fusarium wilt" is one of the most common diseases of the watermelon berry crop and is a big problem for watermelon growers around the world. This disease can deal a huge economic blow to farmers by destroying crops. In this article, we will write information about what alternatives experts offer in the fight against this disease, in addition to the bromide mixture [3,p.252].

References

1. Булгаков Т.С. Микромитеты как патогены клёнов в Ростовской области//Проблемы современной дендрологии, 2009, с.743-747
2. Семенкова И.Г. Лесная фитопатология: учебное пособие. М.:ГОУ ВПО МГУЛ, 2009, 225 с.
3. Мурадов П.З., Гахраманова Ф.Х., Алиев И.А., Аббасова Д.М. и тд. Мониторинг видового состава ксилотрофных макромицетов в лесах Азербайджана/Материалы II Международной научно-практической конференции «Экология биосистем: проблемы изучения, индикации и прогнозирования». Астрахань: Из-во АГУ, 2009, с.252-255.
4. Методы экспериментальной микологии/Под. ред. Билай В.И. Киев: Наукова думка, 1982, 500 с.